
Casos

de Marketing Público y No Lucrativo

XV International Congress on Teaching Cases on Public and
Nonprofit Marketing

Vol 11(2), pp: 50-60

ISSN: 2530-3422 casos-aimpn.org

de Marketing Público e Não Lucrativo

APIVITA:

SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION

Rodoula Tsiotsou

rtsiotsou@uom.edu.gr

orcid:0000-0003-2035-0334

University of Macedonia, Greece

Smaragda Samara

sm.samara@uom.edu.gr

Chrysoula Doulala

bba21184@uom.edu.gr

Athanasia-Sotiria Zafeiri

bba22034@uom.edu.gr

Andromachi Koroniadou

bba22021@uom.edu.gr

Nefeli-Maria Simou

bba21358@uom.edu.gr

Abstract:

Corporations and their activities have a tremendous impact on people's well-being and the environment. Therefore, businesses are required to embrace social responsibility in both their production and operation practices nowadays, with a heightened emphasis on society and the environment. APIVITA is a Greek company that specialized in natural cosmetics. The company's dedication to environmental sustainability is shown in its adherence to the values of authentic clean and ethical beauty, sustainable development, and the acquisition of various awards and recognitions. The purpose of the case study is to highlight the importance of responsible production and consumption, including both business and consumer perspectives. APIVITA distinguishes itself through its commitment to sustainable production methods. To examine consumers' perceptions of APIVITA and its products, we conducted an online survey of 316 individuals. The results of the study indicate that more than half of consumers prefer natural cosmetics, emphasizing that the use of sustainably produced products is very important to them. Moreover, APIVITA is recognized as brand by nearly all the sample and is their top choice in the natural cosmetics market. Finally, the most important reasons consumers use APIVITA products are their natural ingredients and the high perceived quality.

Keywords: *environmental awareness; responsible production; responsible consumption; natural cosmetics; sustainability.*

APIVITA: PRODUCCIÓN Y CONSUMO SOCIALMENTE RESPONSABLE

Resumen:

Las corporaciones y sus actividades tienen un impacto tremendo en el bienestar de las personas y el medio ambiente. Por lo tanto, hoy en día se requiere que las empresas adopten la responsabilidad social

tanto en sus prácticas de producción como en sus operaciones, con un mayor énfasis en la sociedad y el medio ambiente. APIVITA es una empresa griega especializada en cosmética natural. La dedicación de la empresa a la sostenibilidad medioambiental se demuestra en su adhesión a los valores de auténtica belleza limpia y ética, desarrollo sostenible y la adquisición de diversos premios y reconocimientos. APIVITA es una Empresa B desde 2017, lo que demuestra su dedicación a la excelencia social y ambiental. El propósito del estudio es resaltar la importancia de la producción y el consumo responsables, abarcando perspectivas tanto del lado empresarial como del consumidor. APIVITA se distingue por su compromiso con métodos de producción sostenibles. Además, la investigación tiene como objetivo explorar las actitudes y comportamientos de los griegos hacia productos y empresas que se adhieren a métodos de producción sostenibles. Para examinar las percepciones de los consumidores sobre APIVITA y sus productos, realizamos una encuesta en línea a 316 personas. Los resultados del estudio indican que más de la mitad de los consumidores prefieren la cosmética natural, destacando que para ellos es muy importante el uso de productos producidos de forma sostenible. Además, APIVITA es reconocida como marca por casi toda la muestra y es su primera opción en el mercado de la cosmética natural. Finalmente, las razones más importantes por las que los consumidores utilizan los productos APIVITA son sus ingredientes naturales y la alta calidad percibida.

Palabras clave: *advertencia ambiental; producción responsable; consumo responsable; cosmética natural; sostenibilidad.*

1. Introduction

The shift to sustainability involves transforming everyday life into a more environmentally friendly way of life (Vasilopoulou, 2023). According to the United Nations, Sustainable Consumption and Production involve “promoting resource and energy efficiency, sustainable infrastructure, and better quality of life for all” (United Nations, n.d.).

In July 2008, the Commission proposed actions and proposals on Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP) and Sustainable Industrial Policy (SIP) (COM (2008)0397), focusing on improving the environmental performance of products throughout their life cycle (European Parliament, 2023). The EU’s Sustainable Development Strategy (EU SDS) includes various initiatives, such as the Eco-management and Audit Regulation, legislation on Green Public Procurement, the Resource Efficiency Roadmap, and the Eco-Innovation Action Plan. (European Parliament, 2023).

According to the 2023 Sustainable Development Goals Report, under the slogan “Time of crisis, time of change: science to accelerate transformations towards sustainable development,” it is evident that over the past three years, conditions have deteriorated due to the ongoing pandemic, rising inflation, financial crises, and the high cost of living (FINAL GSDR 2023). Regarding the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), there is a significant need for active mobilization from every part of the Earth. Specifically, with this year’s congress theme “Looking into the Future: Conscious of Responsible Production and Consumption.” and the SDG 12 titled “Responsible Consumption and Production”, the goal is “to do more and better with less”, illustrating the increase in the new welfare profit from economic activity and the minimisation of natural resources’ use (United Nations, n.d.).

For these reasons, the current case study aims to examine the sustainable operation and production practices of the Greek company APIVITA, specializing in natural beauty products. The company was selected for the study because it aligns with sustainable production and consumption standards. The name APIVITA is derived from the Latin words “api” (bee) and “vita” (life), signifying “life of the bee”. The company was founded in Athens in 1979 by two pharmacists, Niki & Nikos Koutsianas, who were pioneers in environmental sustainability. Driven by an interest in the life of bees, the variety of Greek natural elements, and guided by scientific principles, the founders developed the initial line of natural cosmetics for the body, hair, and face. The vision of APIVITA prioritizes both people and the environment, aiming for a harmonious blend of experience and emotion coupled with exceptional effectiveness. The company's mission is focused on creating value: "value for the environment, value for society, and value for the economy." (APIVITA Inc., 2023g).

APIVITA has garnered significant recognition for its endeavours, especially in the realms of innovation, research, development, and business activities. The company achieved B Corp status since 2017, aligning

with the B Corporation movement, which comprises purpose-driven companies dedicated to promoting the public good while adhering to rigorous standards of social and environmental performance. In 2022, APIVITA confirmed its certification with the B Corporation movement, achieving a score of 172.2 points among over 6.000 members who share common concerns about social and environmental issues. Furthermore, the company promised commitments to its shareholders, establishing ambitious and challenging objectives for the future (APIVITA Inc., 2023c).

Regarding its global presence, APIVITA was acquired by PUIG in 2017 and since then, the company has a rapid international extension. Today, APIVITA generates sales in 50 countries across four continents. More specifically, APIVITA operates in 32 countries in Europe, seven countries in North & South America, seven countries in Asia and in four countries in Africa. Furthermore, APIVITA is a member of B Corporation movement, as mentioned earlier, and organization “1% for the Planet”, both of which have a global impact. (. (APIVITA Inc., 2023a).

Figure 1 The official website of APIVITA, 07/11/2022

2. Case development

2.1 Clean and Responsible Beauty

APIVITA adheres to the principle of "Clean for the skin, clean for the environment" and is committed to crafting high-quality natural cosmetics with a focus on environmental sustainability. The company focus on preserving natural biodiversity highlighting the therapeutic properties of beekeeping products. (APIVITA Inc., 2023f).

It is remarkable that APIVITA's products consist of 85% to 100% natural ingredients, highlighting their commitment to sustainable production. The company actively contributed to the preservation of Greek natural elements by protecting bees, utilizing renewable sources for ingredients, adhering to the CITES agreement (APIVITA Inc., 2023f).

2.2 The commitment to sustainable growth

APIVITA is deeply committed to sustainable growth, and its corporate governance practices, comprising six key principles, align with current legislation and international best practices. The company's policies aim to align employee goals and ensure customer satisfaction, focusing on the following areas:

- Quality
- Environment
- Health and safety at work
- Marketing and communication
- Sustainable development.

It will be difficult to assume that it is a company that overlooks environmental needs and green growth. APIVITA proudly participates in the global movement “1% for the Planet”. The concept behind this initiative is that every company should contribute 1% of its earnings back to the planet, recognizing that these earnings are created because of earth’s gifts. APIVITA allocates 1% of the sales from Bee Sun Safe, Queen Bee product ranges, APIVITA e-shop and Experience Store to non-profit organizations addressing environmental issues, such as protecting biodiversity and bees, and climate change (APIVITA Inc., 2023e).

As mentioned earlier, APIVITA’s mission is to create value for the environment, society, and the economy. All these three aspects contribute to the goal of sustainable growth.

Bees, regarded as nature’s alchemists by APIVITA, are treated with admiration and respect. Excellent beekeeping practices are used to maintain balance in the beehives and the whole ecosystem. Specifically, the use of chemicals is restricted within the beehive, and interventions are conducted with utmost care using natural oils. It is remarkable that APIVITA maintains beehives in the headquarters of the company, for the personnel to feel close to their roots. Furthermore, the company not only provides education in schools and universities but also directly at the beehive locations. Particularly, there are: (a) Bee Schools, offering both theoretical and practical knowledge in elementary schools, (b) Beevents, providing education directly at sale points and (c) Bee Camp, where awareness is raised through holidays organized around the bees. All the above actions contribute to fostering a green mindset and environmental awareness among the younger generation (APIVITA Inc., 2023e).

Moreover, the company is committed to protecting the biodiversity of the natural environment. Traceability of ingredients is ensured through the network of local farmers and beekeepers who align with the company’s principles of sustainable development. APIVITA chooses regional business partners, whose cultivations are environmentally friendly, with a low carbon footprint in terms of water usage and carbon emissions (APIVITA Inc., 2023f).

Lastly, APIVITA strives to reduce its environmental impact aligning with SDG 11 for “Sustainable cities and communities” and SDG 12 for “Responsible production and consumption”. For example, the packages are eco-friendly and 92% of them being recyclable. In APIVITA, half of the plastic bottles are made from recycled materials, and promotional bags are crafted from recycled bottles (APIVITA Official_Site, n.d.). Besides the ecological packaging, APIVITA ensures that environmental awareness is raised among the customers to promote a zero-waste and reduce-reuse-recycle mindset. Moreover, the company’s bioclimatic headquarters exemplify green philosophy. The building’s design resembles a beehive, and its innovative features enable APIVITA to reduce its environmental footprint each year. Specifically, 100% of the energy used comes from renewable sources, waste is minimized through biological waste treatment, and rainwater is collected and reused (APIVITA Inc., 2023e).

Figure 2 SDG 11 and SDG 12 in APIVITA, 07/11/2022

2.3 Awards and distinctions

APIVITA has received substantial recognition for its efforts, especially in the fields of innovation, research, development, and business activities. The company has been a certified B Corp since 2017, aligning itself with the B Corporation movement—a community of purpose-driven companies dedicated to advancing the public good while adhering to rigorous standards of social and environmental performance. (APIVITA Inc., 2023c).

During 2022, APIVITA received two significant awards in recognition of its sustainable and innovative practices. Firstly, the company secured its third award at the Sustainability Awards 2022, specifically in the category of Sustainability Leadership. This acknowledgment positions APIVITA as a pathfinder in sustainability issues, attributed to its use of innovative formulas, ecological packaging, safeguarding biodiversity, and minimizing its energy consumption and ecological footprint in general. Moreover, APIVITA received a prestigious award at Growth Awards 2022. In this evaluation, where around 8,000 Greek companies were assessed, APIVITA was identified as one of the top three companies in the "Research and Innovation" category. This distinction underscores the company's pioneering entrepreneurial methods, encompassing the ESG strategy (Environmental, Social, and Governance), innovative business management in Greece, and digital development. (APIVITA Ink., 2023b)

The company's adopted approach is noteworthy, aiming to transition towards a more environmentally friendly mode of producing to reduce its environmental footprint. As demonstrated above, places utmost importance on taking responsible actions guided by environmental awareness. A commitment to sustainable production and innovative practices over the last year has led to these prestigious distinctions.

Figure 3 The most important impacts & the impact threshold for each material topic as they arise from the Materiality Analysis procedure (Sustainability Report 2018-19)

2.4 Natural Cosmetics: Exploring consumer attitudes and preferences in Greece.

The beauty industry entices numerous new companies to invest, all with the aim of making distinctive choices essential for thriving in the competitive and constantly evolving globalized landscape. According to a study conducted by McKinsey, in 2022, the beauty market recorded a revenue of around 430 billion dollars in 2022, indicating a positive trajectory. Following the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a consistent recovery, and this appears to be positively impacting the beauty market. Forecasts indicate that the industry is anticipated to reach approximately \$580 billion by 2027, with an annual growth rate of 6 percent.

Successful brands strive to adjust to evolving market dynamics by creating a distinct value proposition for the increasingly sophisticated consumers, considering the following factors:

The rise of wellness: Consumers are increasingly turning to beauty products and services not only for aesthetic appeal, but also for overall well-being.

The influence of Gen Z: Gen Z meticulously evaluates brands before making purchases. Nearly half of Gen Z respondents conduct thorough research on product ingredients and benefits prior to buying. Moreover, Gen Z emphasizes that brands prioritize sustainability, diversity, and inclusion, showing a preference for those with an authentic and relatable image to both consumers and society at large.

The imperative to internationalize: Brands are compelled to expand significantly through diverse distribution channels. Among the 46 companies established in 2005 or later, with global retail sales ranging from \$50 million to \$200 million by 2017, only five exceeded \$250 million in global sales five years later in 2022.

The increase in mergers and acquisitions (M&A): It is evident that there is a significantly increased propensity of financial investors to invest in promising brands. Furthermore, the criteria for M&A targets are expected to shift from a focus on independent high growth "momentary" brands to those with innovative products lines and a proven ability to achieve profitable, sustainable, and enduring growth. (McKinsey & Company, 2023).

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, introduced in 2015, establishes a shared framework for fostering peace and prosperity for both people and the planet. This ambitious agenda outlines 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aimed at addressing various global challenges (United Nations, 2023).

Understanding consumer behaviour within the broader societal context is crucial, especially in terms of their contribution (or not) to sustainable consumption. Equally important is the examination of how consumers interact with businesses and organizations advocating for sustainable production, thereby contributing to the broader objective of sustainable development.

3. Method

To delve into the mentioned aspects thoroughly, an online survey was conducted from 11 to 12 November 2023, among Greek consumers. The primary objective was to investigate consumer attitudes and preferences regarding natural cosmetics in a broader context, with a particular emphasis on their perceptions of APIVITA. The questionnaire consisted of three parts, encompassing both open-ended and closed questions. Part I gathered demographic data, part II collected data on consumers' attitudes and behaviour regarding natural cosmetics and companies that endorse sustainable development. Finally, part III gathered data on consumers' perceptions of APIVITA and its products.

3.1 Sample Profile

The sample of the study consisted of 316 individuals responded to the questionnaire, of which 12% were men and 88% were women. Regarding age, 61% of the sample was between 18 and 39 years old, 36% were between 40 and 59 years old, and the remaining 1% preferred not to answer. Also, 41% of the sample was married, 25% were single, 24% were in a relationship, 6% were divorced, and 3% preferred not to answer. Concerning income, 30% reported an income below 4,999 euros, 18% between 5,000 and 9,999 euros, 26% between 10,000 and 19,999 euros, 8% between 20,000 and 29,999 euros, 2% between 30,000 and 49,999 euros, and the remaining 16% preferred not to answer.

Additionally, regarding the educational background of the respondents, the following emerges: 20% hold postgraduate degrees or higher, 30% are graduates of higher education, 46% have completed secondary education, 2% completed primary education, and finally, 2% preferred not to answer. With regard to their current employment situation, more than half of participants (65%) stated that they were employed (part-time or full-time).

4. Results

We can outline the following fundamental findings:

_ Over 60% of the sample prefer natural cosmetics, emphasizing that the use of sustainably produced products is either very important (58%) or extremely important (29%).

_ The main factors shaping the purchasing choices of the sample in natural cosmetics include friends (31%), advertising campaigns (27%), and family (21%). Additionally, considerations such as ingredients (33%) and pricing (30%) play a significant role.

_ The primary motivation behind the purchase of natural cosmetics by the consumers of the sample is the belief in their superior quality (31%).

_ Fewer than 50% of the sample (40%) refrain from using natural cosmetics, with the majority expressing the belief that these products are expensive (31%).

More specifically, regarding the company APIVITA, the following results are obtained:

In response to the question of whether they are familiar with the company APIVITA, 99% of the sample answered that they know it, and 80% of them use one or more of its products. Additionally, the most significant reasons consumers use APIVITA products are their high content of natural ingredients (26%) and the perceived high quality (23%) that characterizes them.

Furthermore, APIVITA appears to be the top choice among the respondents, with a preference rate of 43%. Particularly important is the observation that 95% of consumers express the intention to repeat the purchase of the company's products and 94% of them will recommend it to others.

Figure 3 The most significant reasons why consumers repurchase products from APIVITA.

5. Questions/issues for discussion

Question 1. *How does the integration of SDG 12 affect APIVITA's role in the global economy?*

As has already been mentioned, the 12th goal among the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals is "Responsible Consumption and Production." Both consumption and production are crucial to the global economy. The damage to human health and the environment caused by humans primarily arises from the phenomenon of irresponsible production and consumption. Considering that most of the 17 SDGs involve actions directly linked to productive activities (such as health insurance, poverty alleviation, clean water security, etc.), it becomes clear that SDG 12 serves as a pillar for the others (Chan et al., 2018). For companies to be profitable today without harming either the economy or the environment, they must strive for long-term profit (Phan et al., 2020). Modern management suggests that companies focus on stakeholders' concerns to achieve the company's goals and implement a stakeholder-based strategy (Lehtinen, J., Aaltonen, K. & Rajala R., 2019).

John Elkington was the first to talk about the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) theory in 1994. According to this theory, a company's evaluation is based on three indicators: its performance in social, economic, and environmental factors (Ahmad & Buniamin, 2021). It is considered that the balance of these three factors enables a company to operate in a more sustainable way (Henriques & Richardson 2004). APIVITA's corporate culture embodies this theory through its operations. Decisions at APIVITA are made responsibly, considering the impact on stakeholders, while creating value for the economy, society, and the environment (APIVITA, Official_Site, n.d.). Thus, the activities of this company are aligned with the commitment to responsible production, such as sustainable production processes, and consumption. Additionally, our research indicates that consumers prefer products that are sustainably produced, contributing to responsible practices without harming the global economy.

Question 2. *In what ways does APIVITA maintain a positive reputation?*

It is a fact that adopting a green mindset in companies offers numerous benefits, with a good reputation

being one of them (Kotler, 2010). This mindset can be fostered through sustainable marketing. Specifically, sustainable marketing entails promoting the value of environmental awareness and engaging in honest and transparent practices. This approach builds trustworthy relationships between companies and consumers, ultimately enhancing the companies' reputations (West, 2022). Additionally, the marketing mix, known as the 4Ps of marketing (product, price, place, promotion), can be an effective strategy for companies aiming for sustainability. However, it's crucial for companies to transform these 4Ps into sustainable practices. For the first 'P' (product), production should align with more sustainable methods, while for the other 'Ps' (price, place, promotion), companies need to strike the right balance to achieve sustainability (Bhalerao & Deshmukh, 2015).

APIVITA's primary goal is to achieve sustainable production to protect the environment and biodiversity. This commitment is realized by following SDG 11 for 'Sustainable cities and communities' and SDG 12 for 'Responsible production and consumption.' This achievement not only provides credibility to consumers but also enhances APIVITA's reputation. In today's consumer landscape, there is a growing demand for environmentally friendly products, as supported by the research. APIVITA maintains its positive reputation primarily through its commitment to sustainability, upholding values that emphasize environmental protection and promoting a "green" mindset. In addition, its recognition and certification by reputable organizations, the high quality of its products, and its participation in the "1% for the Planet" movement positively affect its reputation. The company's commitment to educational initiatives to strengthen consumers' environmental awareness contributes to this direction.

Question 3. *What is APIVITA's attitude in social media and how can it promote its sustainable and environmental awareness through them?*

Like all companies, APIVITA needs to attract and retain potential and existing consumers. Heavy use of social media is employed to reach the desired target audience. Marketing, being an established science, must adapt to new data continuously to meet consumer needs and anticipate developments (Saravanakumar & SuganthaLakshmi, 2012). APIVITA actively engages with its audience on social media, garnering thousands of likes and views for the videos and posts it shares. This success was acknowledged with two awards at the Social Media Awards in Athens (2023), marking a significant achievement for the company and serving as motivation to continue evolving and receiving further recognition (APIVITA Inc, n.d.).

Furthermore, APIVITA maintains an active presence on social media, with over 3,000 posts on Instagram, informing and inspiring its 253 thousand followers. Additionally, it has 452 thousand likes on Facebook and has collaborated on over 140 videos on YouTube with various social media personalities and celebrities. This correlation between the company's declared vision and its promotional activities is evident (APIVITA Greece, n.d.).

The content is carefully designed with vibrant colours, reinforcing the vision of sustainable production. APIVITA ensures that its posts feature images of thriving plants and trees, with a consistent presence of bees, the source of its inspiration.

Through our survey analysis, it became apparent that consumers place great importance on the company's promotion. Specifically, 27% of the respondents indicated that their purchasing decisions are influenced by APIVITA's advertising and promotional campaigns.

Question 4. *What makes sustainable production and consumption crucial for the younger generations?*

As we have observed, previous generations were not particularly interested in environmental issues, and as a result, today's generation is facing the consequences of their predecessors' attitudes. This is the main reason people have become more environmentally conscious, leading to a significant reduction in physical raw materials. With easier access to information, modern consumers have shifted their product choices towards a more sustainable framework. Companies that operate responsibly and seek to reduce their environmental footprint have witnessed significant growth in sales and reputation.

According to sustainable marketing principles, companies need to emphasize environmental and social responsibilities, addressing various forms of pollution and moral issues in society. Several factors are crucial to achieving this:

1. Reduction of environmental footprint.
2. Development of eco-friendly products and sustainable materials.
3. Contributions to sustainable causes.
4. Transformation of company buildings and workspaces into more environmentally friendly settings.
5. Promotion of mass transportation for employees (LaFleur, 2023).

APIVITA adheres to the above factors through the protection of bees and the natural environment, the sustainable management of resources and the use of recyclable packaging. In addition, in 2013, APIVITA upgraded its building to a more sustainable version and switched to 100% green energy (renewable energy sources), reducing water use and waste through composting initiatives (APIVITA Inc., 2023e). According to the research referenced in the development of this case study, over 60% of Greek consumers prefer herbal products, with APIVITA being the top choice for 43% of consumers.

6. Conclusions

Committed to environmental, social, and economic values, APIVITA has successfully created high quality products. The company is known for its sustainable mindset, showing deep respect for the Earth. Its products, which are inspired by bees and the Greek landscape, are recognized for the benefits that their use offers to the human body.

It is evident that APIVITA remains committed to fulfilling its mission and achieving its goal of sustainable development. In particular, the company is aligned with SDG 11 for "Sustainable cities and communities" and SDG 12 for "Responsible production and consumption" to actively protect biodiversity. Additionally, APIVITA achieves this by partnering with local businesses that prioritize environmental sustainability. The company's primary goal is to raise awareness among younger generations about environmental protection in the production process, encouraging them to adopt a green mindset.

Today's globalized and constantly changing market poses significant challenges for most companies. Choosing to prioritize factors such as wellness, the influence of Gen Z, internationalization and mergers and acquisitions (M&A) is crucial to achieving sustainable growth.

Regarding the data obtained from the recent research on natural cosmetics and APIVITA products conducted in Greece, it is worth noting that a significant percentage of Greek consumers use natural cosmetics, emphasizing the importance of sustainable production. Additionally, friends, family, advertising, ingredients, and pricing appear to significantly influence the choice of an herbal product. Companies aspiring to sustainable growth should consider these factors.

In addition, the survey shows that almost all participants are familiar with APIVITA and a significant percentage of them use its products because of their natural ingredients and high quality. This result indicates that APIVITA is successfully meeting its goals.

Potential future research could involve a more extensive population sample, allowing for the generalization of results to the broader population. Exploring the impact of sustainable production and consumption at both micro and macro levels would provide valuable insights. Additionally, conducting investigations into companies and organizations, both locally and internationally, that adhere to sustainable practices in their production processes would be advantageous for academia, the business sector, and society at large. APIVITA stands as a compelling model for other cosmetic companies to delve into more environmentally friendly production processes, and these initiatives should be considered in the future.

Bibliographic references

Ahmad, N., & Buniamin, S. (2021). The Relationship between SDG Engagement and Corporate Financial Performance: Evidence from Public Listed Companies in Malaysia. *Business and Research: An International Journal*, 13(4s), 730. Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from: <http://www.gbmrjournal.com/pdf/v13n4s/V13N4s->

[64.pdf](#)

APIVITA. (n.d.). Sustainability Report 2018-2019. [online] APIVITA. Retrieved 15 Nov.2023 from: https://assets.apivita.com/media/pdf/APIVITA_CSR_2018-2019_ENG.pdf

APIVITA. (2023a). APIVITA Pollinates Beauty in 50 countries all over the world. Retrieved 16 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/en/blog/apivita-pollinates-beauty-in-50-countries-all-over-the-world>

APIVITA. (2023b). APIVITA was awarded at the Social Media Awards 2023. Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/hellas/blog/h-apivita-bravbeuthke-sta-social-media-awards-2023>

APIVITA. (2023c). B-Corporation. Retrieved 12 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/en/b-corporation-b-corp-better-for-the-world>

APIVITA. (2023d). B-Corporation. Retrieved 10 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/hellas/b-corporation-b-corp-kalyteroi-gia-ton-kosmo>

APIVITA. (2023e). Commitments. Retrieved 10 Nov.2023 from:

<https://www.apivita.com/hellas/commitments>

APIVITA. (2023f). Formulas. Retrieved 08 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/hellas/formulas>

APIVITA. (2023g). Origins and Vision. Retrieved 08 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.apivita.com/en/origins>

APIVITA Greece [@apivitagreece]. (n.d.). Instagram. Retrieved 18 Nov. 2023, from <https://www.instagram.com/apivitagreece/>

Bhalerao, V. R., & Deshmukh, A. (2015). Green Marketing: Greening the 4Ps of Marketing. International Journal of Knowledge and Research in Management and E-Commerce, 5(2), 6-7. Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from:https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Vaibhav-Bhalerao-2/publication/310345086_Green_Marketing_Greening_the_4_Ps_of_Marketing/links/582c1dfe08ae102f0720ac7e/Green-Marketing-Greening-the-4-Ps-of-Marketing.pdf

Chan, S., Weitz, N., Persson, Å., & Trimmer, C. (2018). Stockholm Environment Institute SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production - A Review of Research Needs. [online] Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.sei.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/review-sdg12-research-needs-final.pdf>

EUR-Lex, Access to European Union Law. Retrieved 15 Nov.2023 from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02009R1223-20190813#B-3>

European Commission, Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs. Retrieved 15 Nov.2023 from: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/cosmetics/legislation_en

European Parliament. (2023). Sustainable Consumption and Production. Retrieved 07 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/77/sustainable-consumption-and-production>

Henriques, A., & Richardson, J. (Eds.). (2004). The Triple Bottom Line: Does It All Add Up (1st ed.). Routledge. Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781849773348>

Kotler, P., Setiawan, I., & Kartajaya, H. (2010). Striving for Environmental Sustainability. Marketing 3.0. Retrieved 15 Nov.2013 from:

https://www.academia.edu/81638986/Striving_for_Environmental_Sustainability?f_r=18845

LaFleur, G. (2023). 5 best practices for sustainable marketing strategy. Retrieved 17 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcustomerexperience/tip/Best-practices-for-a-sustainable-marketing-strategy>

Lehtinen, J., Aaltonen, K., Rajala, R. (2019). Stakeholder management in complex product systems: Practices and rationales for engagement and disengagement. Industrial Marketing Management, 79, 58-70. Retrieved 17 Nov. 2023 from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019850117308994>

McKinsey & Company. (2023). The Beauty Markets in 2023: A special State of Fashion Report.

Retrieved 18 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/retail/our-insights/the-beauty-market-in-2023-a-special-state-of-fashion-report#>

Phan, T.T.H., Tran, H.X., Le, T.T., Nguyen, N., Pervan, S. & Tran, M.D. (2020). Practices and financial performances: A case study of textiles firms in Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 12. Retrieved 17 Nov. 2023 from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su12155930>.

Rebeka-Anna Pop, Zsuzsa Săplăc, Mónika-Anetta Alt (2020). Social Media Goes Green: The Impact of Social Media on Green Cosmetics Purchase Motivation and Intention. Retrieved 10 Nov. 2023 from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2078-2489/11/9/447>

Saravanakumar, M., SuganthaLakshmi, T. (2012), Social Media Marketing. Retrieved 15 Nov.2023 from: https://www.lifesciencesite.com/lj/life0904/670_13061life0904_4444_4451.pdf

United Nations. (2023). Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns. [Retrieved 07 Nov.2023 from: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal12>

United Nations. (2023). Responsible Production and Consumption. Retrieved 07 Nov.2023 from: <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/page/responsible-production-and-consumption>

United Nations (2023). Final Global Sustainable Development Report 2023. Time of crisis, time of change, science of accelerating transformations to sustainable development, introduction, pp. 19. Retrieved 08 Nov. 2023 from: https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2023-09/FINAL%20GSDR%202023-Digital%20-110923_1.pdf

United States: John Wiley & Sons Inc. p.166. Retrieved 15 Nov.2023 from: https://www.academia.edu/81638986/Striving_for_Environmental_Sustainability?f_ri=18845

Vasilopoulou, X. (2023). The adoption of new habits by citizens towards sustainable development. Retrieved 9 Nov. 2023 from: <https://dione.lib.unipi.gr/xmlui/handle/unipi/15361>

West, Dylan (2022). What Is Sustainable Marketing and Why Is It Important in 2022. Green Business Bureau. Retrieved 17 Nov. 2023 from: <https://greenbusinessbureau.com/business-function/marketing-sales/what-is-sustainable-marketing-and-why-is-it-important-in-2021/>